

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE SOCIAL ORDER FOR MILITARY-PATRIOTIC WORK

Botirova Sayyora Yakubjonovna

Emu university Associate professor of the
department of social sciences,
Doctor of philosophy (phd).

Nargiza Khakimova

2nd-year student, EMU, Fundamental Medicine
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Abstract: This article analyzes the content and significance of the social mandate for military-patriotic education. The role of military-patriotic education in the development of society, state security, and the protection of national interests is highlighted. It also reveals the influence of social order on the formation of feelings of loyalty to the Motherland, civic responsibility, national pride, and respect for military service in the younger generation. The article also examines the cooperation of educational institutions, families, mahallas, and public organizations in the development of military-patriotic education. As a result of the study, it is substantiated that the effective implementation of the military-patriotic social order is an important factor in the spiritual and moral development of youth and the strengthening of the country's defense potential.

Keywords: military patriotism, social order, loyalty to the Motherland, youth upbringing, civic responsibility, national pride, military service, state security, spiritual education.

The social order of military patriotism is a strategic task necessary to strengthen the defense potential of society and the state, educate the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism, and ensure national security. In a broad sense, this concept refers to a set of social needs aimed at implementing military-patriotic tasks facing the state and society.

The priority direction of educating youth in the military-patriotic spirit and the Action Program for its implementation are also specifically highlighted in the State Concept of educating youth in the military-patriotic spirit. According to this Concept, "the goal of state policy in the field of military-patriotic education is to form in young people from early childhood basic concepts and patriotic feelings regarding the duty and constitutional obligation to protect and glorify the Motherland, selflessness, and readiness to realize their civic ideals." This defines the problem of searching for and improving the ways and means of educating citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the spirit of patriotism. One of these ways is the formation of a culture of patriotism in students. Solving the problem of forming a patriotic culture among students is linked to clarifying the concept of "patriotic culture among youth," which becomes clear when its content, structure, and content are revealed. The structure and content of culture allow for the identification of patriotism as one of its essential elements. Our focus is on students as a social structure of youth. The specific characteristics of student youth and their lifestyle (academic activity, preparation for the chosen profession, activity in independent knowledge acquisition, special opportunities for organizing leisure time, communication, the desire for change, lack of life experience, etc.) form a culture of patriotism in them. This can manifest in an indirect form—in the attitude toward learning—as preparation for active participation in the future development of the country, increasing its international prestige, and strengthening the state's defense capability. This requires, in the process of acquiring professional knowledge,

the experience of taking pride in the contribution of compatriots in the past and our time to the development of a particular profession. A high level of interest in acquiring in-depth professional knowledge is also required, which is also an element of the student's patriotic culture. In the process of socio-historical activity, the individual acts not according to an abstract scheme, but in various socially necessary forms, solving socially necessary problems in a unique way, directing their will and activity toward searching for optimal ways to solve these problems.

Therefore, when studying activity as a social necessity, the researcher must determine how the individual becomes a subject of the socio-historical process, what social significance their behavior has, and how they acquire a sense of patriotism. Let us note another important aspect arising from the philosophical analysis of love in the development of patriotic culture: it is a process of development. The awareness of one's Motherland and the feeling of love for it do not arise immediately. And everyone has their own path. A person who has grown up feels a connection to their friends, their hometown, their village, their city. As he grows up and acquires experience and knowledge, he gradually realizes that he belongs to the Motherland and is responsible for it. A citizen is born this way, a patriot is formed this way. But we emphasize once again that this process is complex and contradictory. In his Address to the Oliy Majlis, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, noted: "The mastery of modern knowledge, the desire to be enlightened and highly cultured, must become a vital necessity for all of us." Based on the idea of "From national revival to national development," educating youth in the spirit of patriotism and devotion to the Motherland is our most important task. Attempts to determine the relationship between the concepts of "patriotism" and "culture" lead many authors to different opinions about the place and role of patriotism in culture. Many authors limit themselves to including the analyzed concept only in the title of the work or use it partially in the text without defining the content and content.

In the scientific literature, there is no clear and unambiguous definition of it, and sometimes it becomes a beautiful title of the article without revealing its essence. There are attempts at formulation, which are divided into several interpretations.

1. Comparative - patriotism and culture. Patriotism is perceived as a holistic formation that arises as a result of human intervention in the spiritual culture of society and is a more stable independent formation. The concepts are closely related to each other.

2. Unifying. I.F. Kharlamov combines patriotism and culture into a specific moral quality, which is "the necessity of faithfully serving one's homeland, the manifestation of love and devotion to it, the realization and sensation of its greatness and majesty, a spiritual connection with it, the protection of its honor and dignity, and the practical consolidation of power and independence."

3. Subordination - patriotism in culture. The system of patriotism is defined as a formative philosophical value. Patriotism is formed only in the sphere of culture, in the system of national interests and priorities. Based on national, genuine patriotic feelings, it is open to the perception of other cultures, but at the same time remains rooted in its ancestors, national spiritual and thematic-practical experience; patriotism manifests as a spiritual value in historical retrospection. Patriotism is an integral part of culture.

4. Enhanced - patriotic culture. The high or low culture of patriotism primarily expresses the spiritual essence of a person's attitude toward their Motherland and toward all of humanity. Such patriotism includes a worldview with a moral ideal, which is the spiritual perfection of the

individual in the process of activity for the benefit of the Motherland as a part of all humanity. At the same time, one can observe the constant influence of the moral ideal on the formation of the personality. Patriotic culture, as part of culture, develops through the accumulation of historical experience. Ronald Inglehart noted, "Culture is not permanent. It is a system in which society adapts to its environment. If the environment changes, culture can change after a certain period of time".

Any culture is based on a combination of new and traditional elements of patriotic consciousness and people's behavior. It is this property that allows society to improve its ability to accumulate gains and adapt to environmental changes. This concept allows for the identification of a unit of specialized knowledge that reveals the essence and content of patriotism as a specific relationship between an individual or group and their people and the territory in which they live. This also allows for a more vivid manifestation of values such as love for the Motherland, care for its well-being, and pride in achievements in all spheres of public life. The role of social practices aimed at protecting the Motherland, increasing political and economic power, and increasing prestige in the world is emphasized. At the same time, specific conditions require strengthening one or another element of patriotic culture, eliminating the dangers of nationalism and chauvinism, and replacing the interests of the entire people with the personal needs of the state, rulers, individual social groups, and parties.

The significance of forming a sense of faith in the prosperity of the Motherland today is that the Motherland is a concept that embodies a person's psyche, lifestyle, consciousness and thinking, past, present and future. Acquiring theoretical and practical knowledge of military-patriotic education for students and youth, preparing them for comprehensive military service, and fulfilling their duty to protect the prosperity of Independent Uzbekistan is considered one of the important tasks of the pedagogical collectives of educational institutions. The subject "Military-Patriotic Education" will assist in its successful resolution. The successful resolution of issues regarding the strengthening of the country's defense is closely linked to the upbringing of youth, their political consciousness, labor activity, and the pace of scientific and technological development. Upbringing consists of objectively grounded processes aimed at orienting people toward physical and mental labor or other useful activities for society, as well as preparing them for the fulfillment of multifaceted social tasks. Military-patriotic education is an integral part of it. The methodology and scientific foundations of military-patriotic education are applied to the human factor. This concept includes a set of ideological, political, spiritual, physical, and other human qualities. The theoretical and practical foundations of military-patriotic education include the Constitution of Uzbekistan, the ideas of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on patriotism and the defense of the independent Motherland, laws and resolutions of the Oliy Majlis, orders and instructions of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education, the Ministry of Public Education, the Ministry of Defense, military pedagogy and psychology, military sciences, and other rules and regulatory documents. The main document on the defense of the Motherland is reflected in the Law "On Defense." This Law defines the legal foundations for the organization of defense and the management of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, defines the powers of state bodies, as well as the participation of citizens' self-government bodies, enterprises, institutions, organizations, and citizens in ensuring the country's defense. The historical task of our Armed Forces is to protect the independence of the young country, which has embarked on the path of independent development and the renewal of social relations, as a guarantee of the peaceful life of the people

and the security of the country. Love for the Motherland and the land is a quality deeply ingrained in the hearts of our people, possessing an ancient national character. One of the main tasks of our state is to form a constant readiness to resist any aggression in the human mind using the methods and forms of military-patriotic education, to educate in the spirit of personal responsibility for the defense of one's Motherland.

The widespread use of pedagogical and psychological rules in the military-patriotic education of student youth is of great importance. The great enlightener Abdulla Avloni said: "Science is the wealth of the world. Knowledge is a person's highest and most sacred achievement. For knowledge, like a mirror, shows us our worldview and our aspirations. Like a sword, it sharpens our minds and thoughts. Morality is, first and foremost, a sense of conscience. This is trust and honesty. Our ancestors developed a set of criteria for the moral evaluation of a person and, in modern terms, created the "Eastern Code of Ethics." Resistance must arise in the human heart to those who do not earn their bread honestly, to dishonesty, to dishonesty. Only such a person keeps his word, does not covet the rights of others, does not spare his life for the defense of his Motherland and people, and, on the contrary, is a liar, a chatterbox, and has no sense of patriotism. Any evil deed, selfishness, or malice is a betrayal of the Motherland. Morality is one of the forms of social consciousness, a set of rules of behavior that people living in a particular society must follow. Morality manifests in a system of behavioral rules that regulate people's relationships to each other, society, the state, public property, the family, the Motherland, and the motherland. Morality is a set of requirements, norms, and rules accepted by society, imposed on the behavior of people in society, in the family, at work, in relationships with one another, and with themselves. It is emphasized that the builder of a democratic society must work honestly for the happiness of society, have a high awareness of social duty, and be honest, truthful, moral, simple, and modest in social and personal life. It is of great importance that our military-patriotic student youth, on the one hand, demonstrate what they are capable of through selfless education and upbringing and increasing their level of profound knowledge, while also demonstrating their behavior, morality, and spiritual beauty. At the same time, by demonstrating selflessness, patriotism, and humanity in the most difficult spheres of labor and creativity, they remain a source of warm inspiration for the respect and love of society. This is because we are faced with the task of raising harmoniously developed successors who have freed themselves from the shackles of the past, possess their own independent thoughts, and are capable of demonstrating selflessness in the interests of their nation and Motherland. Military psychology, which studies the psychological activity of cognition in the conditions of military service in peacetime and combat situations, is also of great importance for organizing military-patriotic education. Psychological science helps to better understand the correct organization of military-patriotic education with people who differ in personality, inner spiritual world, behavioral factors, characteristics, and interests. Good knowledge of psychological science by educators will help them successfully resolve issues of professional selection and the preparation of high school students for admission to military educational institutions and service in various types of activities and the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Military-patriotic education of youth is also a military science that reveals the nature of modern warfare, the means and forms of armed combat, its legality, and the conditions of combat operations, and is organized taking into account its rules and conclusions. Military science answers questions about what moral, political, psychological, and combat qualities a

person must possess and what knowledge and skills are necessary for them to successfully fulfill their duty as defenders of the Motherland. The principles of military-patriotic education are inherently objective. They are a reflection of the actual situation, real connections and relations, and the scientifically grounded, purposeful activity of state and public organizations in preparing the people for the defense of the country.

Currently, it is of great importance to develop a sense of patriotism in our youth and to educate them in the spirit of love and devotion to the Motherland. A person must love their country as it is and use all their potential for its development. Patriotism manifests in people mainly in three stages: 1) knowledge - mastering the values inherent in the concept of the Motherland;

2) conviction - the transformation of knowledge about these values into conviction; 3) action is the manifestation of faith through practical deeds.

Historically, patriotism is also a set of feelings that have evolved in the process of social development related to the fate of one's homeland and the struggle of peoples for the inviolability and independence of the territory in which they live. This is manifested in pride in the past and present of the motherland and in defending its interests. It is not for nothing that they say that love for the Motherland comes from faith. There are many patriotic people in our country. For example, although Abdulla Avloni lived during the years of repression, freedom of speech was very developed in him. Mahmudkhodja Behbudi is known in our country for his books on teaching children. His work on teaching children foreign languages, literacy and other education is worthy of attention. In the work of our first president "High spirituality is an invincible force" there is a lot of information about the contributions of our ancestors to their native lands, for example, the resistance to the oppression of Genghis Khan, the courage of Amir Temur, Jaloliddin Manguberdi and other great commanders.

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